

RENEWAL OF THE OPERATION OF THE EU CUSTOMS SYSTEM IN HUNGARY

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Abstract

This study examines how Hungary's budget revenues have changed because of customs duties. On May 1, 2004, the European Union was further expanded by the fact that Hungary also joined the membership, and after the accession, Hungary also joined the customs policy of the EU. But this is not the only significant change. No public data sources exist on which countries and goods are delivered to the community at what customs price. However, the amount of revenue from customs revenues has decreased. The situation is also complicated by the fact that the territory of the European Union and the location of the customs border do not coincide. At the same time, there was a significant change in the reliability and speed of customs activities. Hungary's budget revenues changed significantly after joining the European Union in 2004. There will be a significant change in the accuracy and speed of completion of customs declarations, which will bring about changes in customs clearance processes. The proposals can be exemplary for other middle-income countries, such as Hungary, and for higher-income EU countries in terms of application to EU regulations.

Keywords:

AIS-AES, budget revenue, customs duty, customs system, tax

1 Introduction

In the last two decades, a dramatic and fundamental change has occurred in many advanced economies' budgetary policies. These recent debt and financial crises and their negative spillover effects on several emerging economies have brought the potential damage to the fore. Policymakers and academics have, therefore, recently made efforts to try to predict financial and debt crises before they occur. That is why the countries in the European Union must prepare a stable and sustainable budget and minimise their possible deficit state. For the expenses not to significantly exceed the incomes, the incomes must be raised close to the level of the expenses. The revenues from public finances are made up of several parts. One significant source of income was the duties established during import customs procedures, which were a very significant source of the budget. The lack of coordination of tax policies across the European Union allows multinational enterprises to shift profit and avoid their fair share of tax payments (Nerudova et al., 2023).

Since our membership in the European Union, the role of customs revenues in the budget has decreased significantly. However, this is not the only significant change; it is also the fact that we know much less about EU customs revenues. No public data sources exist on which countries and goods are delivered to the community at what customs price. Small and medium-sized enterprises constitute a significant industrial segment (Prashar, 2017).

Like the other member states of the European Union, Hungary plays a decisive role in promoting international trade through its customs activities. The EU's customs system is vital

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in maintaining the smooth flow of goods between member states and the integrity of the single market. This article explores the renewal of the operation of the EU customs system in Hungary and its effects on trade and border management.

Changes occurred in connection with Brexit (Muinzer et al., 2022). Northern Ireland remains part of the common customs area, but the United Kingdom is no longer part of the European Union. However, the unity of the Customs Union did not cease. Although Turkey, Andorra, and San Marino are not EU member states, they still form a duty-free zone with the Customs Union of the European Union.

2 Research Methodology

The research methodology used during the renewal of the Hungarian EU customs system includes a comprehensive assessment of the existing customs procedures, including a thorough evaluation of performance and identifying deficiencies. The legal framework governing customs operations is regularly reviewed and updated to meet evolving EU regulations and international trade standards. Technology integration is key, focusing on applying digital tools, automation, and data-sharing mechanisms to increase efficiency. Training and capacity building are prioritised to ensure stakeholders, including customs officials, are adequately prepared for updated procedures and technologies. The renewal process includes rigorous testing and piloting phases to identify and address potential issues before fully implementing the renewed customs system. I consider it appropriate to use the PDCA (Plan-Do-Check-Act) cycle when introducing changes to the customs management system.

PDCA is a systematic and iterative four-step management method for continuously improving processes, products, or services.

- **Plan:** In the first phase, organisations identify and plan for improvement. This involves establishing objectives and goals, identifying processes that need improvement, and devising a plan to achieve those objectives.
- **Do:** The second phase involves implementing the plan. This is where the planned changes are executed, and the new processes, products, or services are implemented.
- **Check:** After the implementation, the next step is to assess and monitor the results. Organisations evaluate whether the implemented changes have achieved the desired goals and objectives.
- **Act:** In the Check phase, organisations act appropriately based on the evaluation. The changes are standardised and incorporated into regular practices if the results meet the objectives. If there are deficiencies or areas for further improvement, the organisation refines the plan and repeats the cycle.

The PDCA cycle is a critical component of many quality management systems. It is widely used in various industries to drive continuous improvement and ensure that organisations adapt and thrive in a dynamic environment.

The PDCA cycle can be combined with a simulation model of the production facility to test different what-if scenarios. This allows strategies to be tested without disturbing the current manufacturing system, significantly reducing the time, cost, and risk of implementing new strategies (Cui et al., 2023).

Fig. 1. PDCA cycle model source

Source: ("BokasTutor, 2023)

2.1 The customs union of the European Union and its changes

The EU's customs system is designed to harmonise customs procedures between member states, promoting efficiency, transparency, and security. This includes the electronic exchange of information between customs authorities, businesses, and other relevant parties. Customs operations are regularly reviewed and updated to address emerging challenges, improve processes, and improve overall efficiency.

The renewal of the EU customs system in Hungary is carried out in cooperation with the Hungarian government and the European Commission. The process is presented in Figure 2. The circular shape represents the ongoing renewal and development of the customs clearance process.

Fig. 2. presents the procedure for renewing the EU customs system in Hungary.

Source: Developed by the authors

2.2 The process includes the following steps:

Before the renewal, a comprehensive evaluation of the existing customs system will be carried out. This includes evaluating performance, identifying weaknesses, and considering technological improvements. After that, they take care of the legal framework. The legal framework governing customs operations will be reviewed and updated to comply with EU regulations and international trade standards. Technological development also requires integration. The technological developments were incorporated to increase the efficiency of customs procedures. This may include introducing and integrating new digital tools, automation, and data-sharing mechanisms. Once implemented, customs officials and relevant stakeholders will be trained to familiarise themselves with the updated procedures and technologies. Capacity building ensures a smooth transition to the renewed system. The new customs system will undergo thorough and pilot testing to identify potential problems before full implementation. This phase allows for adjustments and fine-tuning based on real-world scenarios. After successful testing, the renewed customs system will be officially introduced. This may involve a phased approach to minimise disruption to ongoing commercial activities.

The introduction of a new procedure in customs clearance marks a strategic effort to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of trade processes. This initiative aims to streamline the movement of goods by leveraging innovative methods, potentially reducing delays and administrative complexities in customs operations. During the introduction of the new procedure, the PDCA management cycle model can be identified to support these activities.

The change in the customs clearance process can provide the following benefits for the member countries modernising the customs procedure:

- *Efficiency improvement:* Simplified customs procedures reduce delays and administrative burdens, facilitating faster customs clearance of goods.
- *Enhanced security:* The updated systems enhance the detection of potential risks and strengthen border security measures.
- *Compliance with central regulations:* Alignment with EU regulations ensures that Hungary continues to comply with international trade standards.

2.3 The source of Hungary's budget and the possibilities of the community's income

These budget revenue sources are essential to the European Union (Syropoulos, 2003). They make up about 11%-13% of the budget revenue. Before the accession to the European Union, the total amount of customs duty paid was Hungary's income. From then on, however, the most significant part of this income belongs to the EU, of which the Hungarian member state can take a small part. Eighty per cent of customs revenues belong to the community and the remaining 20 per cent to the countries that collect them. Thus, in the budget, the size of the budget revenue from customs revenues also decreased significantly in all member states. During the redistributive policy, they may later benefit from EU support in a different form, but this study does not deal with this topic (Amores et al., 2023).

Consequently, Hungary's budget revenue from customs payments is no longer significant (Sipos, 2015). The customs revenue of countries with seas and ports is much higher. Hungary earns customs revenues after customs clearances after deliveries by air, container deliveries from 3rd countries delivered here by directional trains, and goods delivered from former Soviet member states located east of Hungary. However, the differences between the individual member countries are significant for the reasons mentioned. Compared to the community's average, the customs revenue measured concerning economic performance in Hungary is one-tenth less. In addition to the costs involved, customs clearance time also creates significant

differences in customs clearance locations. This and the speed of customs clearances justify which countries can encourage more traders to do this activity with better customs services and which nations are better avoided (Elliott & Bonsignori, 2019).

For example, the case of Ireland is also interesting because, although its customs revenues are low, it still has a significant turnover of goods by sea, and most of the products subject to customs duties come by sea from distant China. Therefore, it is evident that the goods have already been cleared at the ports and transported to the continent's interior. For landlocked countries, it is, therefore, understandable if the proportion of customs revenues is lower. Many companies also use this opportunity for the ports of Hamburg, Rotterdam, Trieste, and Koper.

3 Europe's most important seaports

The efficiency and competitiveness of seaports have always been significant for European seaports. In the last 30 years, the ports have undergone many changes, just as the services provided by the ports (customs handling, warehousing, transshipment) have also continuously changed according to the needs (Kammoun & Abdennadher, 2022). Figure 3 shows the most important European ports.

Fig. 3. The most important European ports

Source: (ShipHub, 2021)

The member states have different options regarding the distribution of customs revenues. Austria, Estonia, Slovakia, and Romania came behind Hungary on the list of significant beneficiaries of customs revenue. The Czech Republic can collect nearly a third more customs duties on dutiable imports than Hungary, even without coastal ports. Countries with seaports, such as Germany, the Netherlands, Greece, Spain, Portugal, Italy, and Slovenia, collect the most duties on dutiable imports.

In Hungary, customs revenue and foreign trade are among the highest compared to GDP in the world, so it can be fundamentally misleading to measure the revenue from the payment of customs duties against economic performance. Most imports from European Union countries can be linked to duty-free EU partners. If the proportion of customs duties paid locally reached the EU average in Hungary, it would represent HUF 7.6 billion in additional revenue for the Hungarian budget annually. Customs control depends on the type of transport on which the goods are transported (Fuchs et al., 2022).

Several companies providing preparation and commissioning of customs clearance services were also established. In addition to providing services, these companies also perform warehousing tasks. In addition to completing the customs clearance procedure, they also help the principals with their deferred customs payment permits, for whom a delayed payment of up

to two weeks means significant ease compared to the customs clearance option of the country of the site. Of course, this option also generates costs. The service also has a price. The direct customs clearance fee is now EUR 60–70, based on the number of customs clearances in 2023. The service providers use a bank guarantee certifying the payment of the subsequent customs costs. This is determined at around 2% of the customs value of the imported product. Considering the company's solvency using the service, however, after invoicing the incurred costs, a payment deadline of one month is usually given. The service is in the European Union but not Hungary, so paying VAT is unnecessary. In Hungary, the importer is also obliged to pay the VAT. Although this amount can be reclaimed, it still requires considerable liquidity from the importer despite the possibility of reclaiming the VAT later.

Another case is when, during the declaration of the imported goods for customs clearance, the value of the goods is under-invoiced on the commercial invoice that forms the basis of the customs clearance. The more significant the deficit, the greater the extent of misrepresentation by the importer, which is motivated by the incentive to under-invoice to avoid paying customs duties (Al Wazzan et al., 2023).

The administration in our area is also difficult and bureaucratic. However, this will change after the end of 2023. The use of AIS (Automated Import System) and AES (Automated Export System) is required from the member states of the European Union (Customs Office, Hungary, 2023).

In the case of Hungary, as I mentioned before, the level of customs duties is not significant today. The budget deficit is increased by the direct payment to the EU and the net revenue loss related to the customs system, which is the difference between the lost customs revenues and the reimbursement of customs collection costs paid by the EU. The EU reimbursement will reduce the deficit. Excise tax rates raised due to EU regulations are also linked to EU accession in a completely analogous way to customs reduction. It positively affects the budget that EU funds can be used to finance previous programs at a lower domestic cost.

4 Conclusion

Customs play a crucial role in facilitating and speeding up the international flow of goods, especially in logistic nodes such as seaports or dry ports (Cavallini & Benzi, 2023). The renewal of the EU customs system in Hungary is a dynamic process, aiming to modernise customs operations to the changing needs of international trade.

Fig. 4. The changes from inefficient manual process to the digital era

Source: (Pettit et al., 2022)

By embracing technological developments and adapting to EU standards, Hungary contributes to the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the EU customs system, promoting the smooth flow of goods across borders. Table 1 shows the steps of the changes.

Tab. 1. Summary of the changes in the customs procedure

Previous process			
Submission of customs clearance documents	NAV's feedback	Possible outcome	The administration time
only on paper documents	only on paper documents	only on paper documents	only on paper documents
(commercial invoice, transport document and insurance, goods declaration)	(to present a declaration form, to present certificates, to present a request for goods inspection)	1. Successful customs clearance	Longer procedure
Further process	Change request	2. Further procedure	Longer procedure
New process			
on the electronic way only	on the electronic way only	on the electronic way only	on the electronic way only
(commercial invoice, transport document and insurance, goods declaration)	(to present a declaration form, to present certificates, to present a request for goods inspection)	1. Successful customs clearance	Quick procedure
Further process	Change request	2. Further procedure	Quick procedure

Source: developed by the authors

Moreover, the emphasis on continuous updates to customs clearance processes reflects Hungary's proactive approach to staying ahead of regulatory changes. By adapting to evolving legal requirements and international standards, Hungary ensures that its customs activities remain in harmony with the global trade landscape, fostering strong bilateral and multilateral trade relations. As Hungary positions itself as a critical player in regional and international trade, modernising customs clearance activities is a strategic investment in the nation's economic future. The collaborative efforts between the government, businesses, and international partners underscore Hungary's commitment to creating an efficient, transparent, and secure customs framework that supports sustainable economic development and integration into the broader global economy, as is shown in Figure 4.

This is, of course, not a closed process, as this activity is still ongoing. Companies must develop a competitive advantage in today's competitive business environment. Technological innovation is one of the most effective ways for companies to achieve this advantage and enhance their competitiveness (Mokhtari Moughari & Daim, 2023). The innovations implemented now must be reviewed after a certain period, and if they do not meet expectations, they must be changed again. Figure 4 shows the changes from inefficient manual processes to the digital era.

Before modernising customs clearance activities, Hungary faced inefficiencies, manual processes, and challenges adapting to the digital era of global trade. After embracing modernisation, Hungary now boasts streamlined procedures, reduced processing times, and enhanced security measures, positioning the country as a competitive player in the international trade landscape while fostering a more conducive environment for businesses and ensuring compliance with evolving standards. The transformation underscores Hungary's commitment to economic growth, resilience, and successful integration into the dynamic global trade ecosystem.

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